

CREATING A FEMALE IMAGE IN UZBEK LITERATURE (BASED ON THE EXAMPLE OF ABDULLAH KADIRI'S NOVEL "BYGONE DAYS")

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The thesis describes the importance and influence of national traditions on the upbringing of children. The Uzbek family has its own characteristics. The life and exploits of our great ancestors are not the basic principles of the Uzbek family – they are the sanctity of marriage, the responsibility of parents for raising children and respect for the adult generation.

KEY WORDS

national traditions, upbringing, female image, artistic comparison, object of comparison.

A woman, or rather a mother, is highly respected in society. This situation is clearly stated in the Hadith of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) that "Paradise is under the feet of mothers." Women are responsible for the birth of a person and his upbringing from infancy to adulthood. The comparison of female images of different peoples has always been interesting. The study of the artistic heritage of outstanding authors attracted the attention of a wide range of researchers, linguists and literary critics. Of great interest is the study of the means and techniques used by the authors of fiction to create the imagery of their works and aesthetic impact on the reader. Numerous conferences, discussions, round tables, seminars, etc. are held on the subject of research on issues of spiritual and moral education. The influence of national traditions on the upbringing of children is of great importance. The Uzbek family has its own characteristics. The life and exploits of our great ancestors are not the basic principles of the Uzbek family – they are the sanctity of marriage, the responsibility of parents for raising children and respect for the adult generation. Since prehistoric times, a woman has become an object of "male art". This is what we are told by the so-called "venera" - stone figurines of pregnant women with large breasts. Literature has remained masculine for a long time, because there is also what a man saw in a woman. The woman was and is still the subject of a cult (from the ancient mysteries to the Christian veneration of the Virgin Mary). In Uzbek literature, Abdullah Kadiri's novel "Bygone Days" reveals a wide range of universal themes and problems. Therefore, it is very difficult to define it unambiguously. But still, it can be argued that, having based the work on a beautiful love story, the author managed to touch on the most

difficult problem of the confrontation between God and the devil, light and darkness in the destinies of mankind.

In many ways, Abdullah Kadiri puts his own thoughts and judgments into the mouth of his hero. In parallel, the writer traces the fate of an Uzbek woman. Inhuman and cruel customs, in particular polygamy, lead to a deadly feud between two women - Kumush and Zainab. With special love and sincerity, the writer paints the image of the beautiful Kumush, who, thanks to her pure and all-consuming love for Otabek, overcomes the trials of life and the treachery of enemies. However, tragedy is inevitable. She dies poisoned by them, and Otabek dies in battle with the enemies of his Homeland.

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